

The importance of magnetic measurements dovetailed with chemical analysis for the rapid characterization of heavy metal-bearing urban dust load

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Abstract : Major cities of the world are found to be dangerously close to or exceeding the permissible limit of particulate size in inhalable air (grains size $<10\ \mu\text{m}$). However, the cities with high population density and unique environmental conditions are prone to heavy metal contamination that is reflected in the suspended particulate matter (<http://www.dailymail.co.uk>; Accessed on July 13, 2013). In such cases, metal toxicity in air is monitored on the basis of chemical and/or granulometric analyses requiring expensive instruments and sample preparation technique. Environmental magnetism is a relatively new area of research which uses magnetic properties of the particulate matter to monitor environmental pollution and at the same time it is rapid, quantitative, non-destructive and inexpensive. The present study is a case in hand to reflect the effectiveness of magnetic measurements coupled with selective chemical analysis to show the level of heavy metal contamination in parts of Allahabad city ($25^{\circ}27'33.40''$; $81^{\circ}52'45.47''$), U.P., India covering an area of about 63 sq with a population of near 12 million. The dust samples are collected from road side tree leaves comprising 1052 number of samples during four different sampling periods between January, 2011 and January, 2013 are also analyzed by microscopic, sub-microscopic, chemical, magnetic and XRD techniques. The concentration of elements (Pb, Zn, Ni, Cr and Cd) in dust particulate matter of Allahabad is very high and can be compared to some of the most polluted locations of the world. Interestingly, the magnetic susceptibility values of the dust samples (3.1 and $1262 \times 10^{-8}\ \text{m}^3/\text{kg}$) show a positive correlation with their respective elemental concentrations.

Keywords : Environmental magnetism, heavy metal contamination, dust-loaded tree leaves.

Introduction

In recent years the characterization of dust load by magnetic susceptibility measurements as well as geochemical analysis has become a standard approach in aerosol research^{1,2}. The urban dust load is a collective assemblage of varied size particulate matter derived from lithogenic and/or anthropogenic sources and with or without possible inputs from the cosmogenic sources. The inhalable dust particulate size is an important parameter to evaluate its impact on life forms. Similarly the concentration of heavy metals in the urban dust load is a good indicator of atmospheric pollution vis-à-vis human health. The magnetic concentrations as well as chemical analysis data show seasonal fluctuations (high in thick winter fog period versus low and small in summer, respectively) due to the variation in seasonal influx of anthropogenic material invariably having magnetic constituents.

Material and methods :

The samples of dust particulates per ten dust-loaded

tree leaves were collected from 300 sites of Allahabad city from 4 different deciduous trees of *Ficus benghalensis*, *Ficus religiosa*, *Cassia fistula* and *Anthocephalus cadamba*. The magnetic susceptibility was measured using Bartington dual frequency magnetic susceptibility meter (MS2 B, UK; Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, University of Allahabad) and geochemical analyses are carried out using ICP-MS (Perkin-Elmer SCIEX, Quadrupole type ELAN DRC-e, Wadia Institute of Himalayan Geology, Dehradun) instrument.

Results

The average mineral magnetic measurements and geochemical data are summarized in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The magnetic measurements of fog, post-monsoon and pre-monsoon dust samples collected during the respective years (2011 and 2013, 2011, and 2012) show variation in LF, HF and mass magnetic susceptibility values. The volume magnetic susceptibility values for average 1052 number of samples LF (0.13 to 67), HF

Table 1. Comparison between magnetic parameters such as χ_{LF} values of present study and published values from other countries

Measurements	Units	Range	Mean
χ_{LF} (present study)	$10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$	3.1–1262	194.4
Kim <i>et al.</i> (2007) ³	$10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$	–	62.00
Ovaia <i>et al.</i> (2012)	$10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$	0.21–29.62	9.04

Table 2 Comparison of trace elements analyses (values in parts per million) of average selected leaf dust samples with other countries carried out by ICP-MS technique is given below

Sample details	Pb	Cd	Cr	Zn	Ni
Present study	13–129	0.3–1.96	13–172	95–320	28–172
Kim <i>et al.</i> (2007) ³	61–389	–	31–107	242–393	–
Wei <i>et al.</i> (2009) ⁵	13–99	0.11–14	20.2–174	69–846	–
Nazzari <i>et al.</i> (2013) ⁶	32.5–378	0.46–0.95	57.3–558	–	16–327
Germade <i>et al.</i> (2014) ⁴	–	0.03–0.19	–	–	0.69–3.00

(0.1 to 65.5) and mass magnetic susceptibility (3.1 to 1262) exhibit variation in terms of the nature of the magnetic phase(s) and their concentration. Based on XRD data, the dust samples are found to comprise quartz, feldspar, magnetite, gypsum, biotite mica and illite predominantly and their presence is supported by the magnetic measurements. Forty road dust samples collected from parts of Allahabad city were analyzed for Cd, Cr, Ni, Pb and Zn content using ICP-MS technique. Their concentration is in the ppm range and is variable in space and time. The most dominant amongst the analyzed elements, is Zn (95–320 ppm) and the content of Cd is the least (0.3–1.96 ppm) in these samples.

Conclusions

It is interesting to note that despite having relatively less number of industries and comparatively low traffic volume, the susceptibility values of the particulate matters in all sampling periods are much higher than industrial cities like Seoul, Korea³ and Madrid, Spain⁴ and similarly heavy metals values are also higher (Fig. 1) compared to some developed countries like China⁵ and Canada⁶. In Allahabad city, a positive correlation between magnetic susceptibility data and chemical constituent of the dust load has been established. In the present study the Pb concentration is high possibly derived from anthropogenic sources (like cars, buses and industrial process like thermal power plants). The high concentration of Cr is attributed to the emissions of chromium-based automotive catalytic converters. High concentration of

Zn in the environment possibly comes from both natural and anthropogenic sources (like vehicular rubber tyres). This study suggests the increase of vehicular pollution is one of the main reasons for the rise of pollutants in atmospheric dust in addition to the emission from the only major industrial unit (IFFCO; Indian Farmers Fer-

Fig. 1. Trace elements analyses (values in parts per million) plot of average selected leaf dust samples (present study) and in comparison with published results from other countries.

tilizer Co-operative Limited), a thermal power plant situated in the vicinity of the city at Phulpur.

This finding is also significant since this study shows magnetic susceptibility values are higher than a site-specific threshold. In addition, the present study demonstrates the potential of magnetic susceptibility field mapping for the rapid preliminary site assessment, greatly reducing the scale of subsequent geochemical sampling and analysis. In addition, it is a non-destructive technique and requires samples in mg to gm level which is a boon for leaf dust studies as sample weight is mostly in milligram range.

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